

JURISPRUDENCE

ISSUES OF LEGAL REGULATION OF THE APPLICATION OF SPECIAL KNOWLEDGE IN CRIMINAL PROCEDURE IN RETROSPECTIVE CONTEXT

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Abstract

The historical method acts in legal science as a means of accurately understanding the assessment of law from the standpoint of the past state of its form, content and essence, as well as from the point of view of its true modern significance. However, this does not limit the scientific significance of the historical method, which isolates the specifically legal content, giving it a historical assessment. It can be noted that in the context of the natural relationship between historical and logical, as well as taking into account the combination of theoretical and historical profiles, research and coverage of law is combined with a chronological and problem-categorical method of cognition. Taking into account what was said in the clause, an attempt was made to regulate the use of special knowledge in criminal proceedings in the context of the provisions of the Criminal Procedure Codes of 1923 and 1961.

Keywords: criminal procedure law, special knowledge, expert, specialist, law, duty, expert opinion, law, historical approach, system analysis.

It is known that the retrospective method (derived from the Latin words *retro* meaning "back" and *spec-tare* meaning "to look") is one of the research methods in legal science. As noted in the literature, this or any other form of the method reflects the specific rules, methods, and tools of scientific cognition and practical activity. The method organizes scientific research aimed at achieving relevant goals and outcomes, directing it toward a specific correct path. The primary purpose of any method is conditioned by solving specific cognitive problems, issues related to practice, and enriching scientific knowledge, based on the relevant principles. In legal science, the retrospective, or historical approach method requires studying the emergence of law or its individual institutions, taking into account historical changes and circumstances [4, p.18-19].

The retrospective method is also effectively applied when studying individual criminal procedural law institutions. In this regard, Professor Miragha Ashraf Jafarguliyev notes that criminal procedural law, as one of the essential fields of legal sciences, has undergone numerous studies and changes from its inception to the present day. Criminal procedural legislation, after passing through a unique and rich historical development path, has become the national legislative framework regulating the administration of justice in our modern era. Based on this, when studying criminal procedural law (or its individual institutions), it is appropriate to pay attention to the historical development of criminal procedural legislation, even if briefly [3, p.54].

As a researcher studying the issues related to the application of special knowledge in criminal proceedings, we also believe that examining the legal regulation of the application of special knowledge in the criminal process within a retrospective context holds significant scientific importance. In this regard, the current clause addresses the legal regulation of the application

of special knowledge in criminal proceedings, considering the provisions of the previous two Criminal Procedure Codes (hereafter referred to as CPC) that existed in Azerbaijan before the adoption of the new Criminal Procedure Code in 2000, following the country's independence. As is known, before the current CPC of Azerbaijan, there were two previous CPCs:

1) The first Criminal Procedure Code of the Azerbaijan SSR – adopted on June 16, 1923, and came into force on September 25, 1923 (hereafter referred to as the 1923 CPC);

2) The second Criminal Procedure Code of the Azerbaijan SSR – adopted on December 8, 1960, and came into force on March 1, 1961 (hereafter referred to as the 1961 CPC).

A systematic study of both CPCs indicates that these codes contained provisions related to the procedural-legal status of subjects with special knowledge and the procedural forms for applying special knowledge. Therefore, we have identified and systematized these provisions, summarizing them as follows. It should be noted that, in order to preserve the language and terminological characteristics of the CPCs under review, the terminology used in the provisions reflects the terminology that was relevant during the period when these CPCs were in force.

Thus, in the 1923 CPC, subjects with special knowledge were referred to as *ahl-i-khibra* (which, when literally translated from Arabic, means those who are knowledgeable or experts). In terms of their procedural-legal status, there was no distinction between modern-day experts and specialists. *Ahl-i-khibra* referred to a subject who could be understood as an expert in the modern sense. However, *ahl-i-khibra* not only acted as subjects conducting expert investigations but also participated as specialists in investigative actions in the modern sense. Although the reviewed Code did

not contain a separate clause dedicated to the procedural status of *ahl-i-khibra*, there were several legally significant provisions concerning the legal status of experts and expertise within the content of the Code. Thus, Clause 55 of the 1923 CPC considered the opinions of *ahl-i-khibra* as one of the independent types of evidence. According to the provisions of Clause 60 of the same CPC, *ahl-i-khibra* were to be summoned when special knowledge in science, art, or profession was necessary for the investigation or hearing of the case. Furthermore, according to the first clause of the Note of this clause, it was mandatory to summon *ahl-i-khibra* to determine the cause of death and the nature of bodily injuries, as well as when doubts arose in the court or investigator about the mental state of the defendant or witness. Clause 61 of the reviewed CPC specified that a person summoned as *ahl-i-khibra* was obliged to attend, participate in inspections and examinations, and provide an opinion. In case of failure to attend without a valid excuse or refusal to perform their duties without legal grounds, appropriate measures could be taken against them (such measures included compulsory summons if they failed to attend without a valid excuse, and the sending of the case to the nearest people's court with a protocol if they refused to provide an opinion). Moreover, Clause 62 of the reviewed CPC provided that *ahl-i-khibra* had the right to receive compensation for their expenses and the time they spent away from their regular occupations when summoned, as well as a reward (in the form of a fee) for performing their duties. The amount of money to be given to *ahl-i-khibra* was determined by a special instruction from the People's Justice Commissariat.

In the 1923 CPC, the main provisions determining the procedure for conducting expert examinations were concentrated in Clauses 166-171. According to these provisions, when *ahl-i-khibra* were summoned, the investigator determined their number. If requested by the accused, the investigator could summon an *ahl-i-khibra* selected by the accused, in addition to the expert chosen by the investigator (the summoning of the expert selected by the accused could be refused if it was not possible to summon the specified *ahl-i-khibra*, or if there was a risk of delaying the preliminary investigation). Before questioning the *ahl-i-khibra*, the investigator was required to:

- verify their identity;
- inform them that they were required to provide an opinion strictly related to the specifics of the case and the special knowledge for which they were summoned;
- warn them about the responsibility for refusing to give an opinion and for providing false opinions.

The provisions in the current CPC (Clause 140) regarding mandatory cases for appointing expert examinations can be considered as predecessors to the provisions in the Note, paragraph 1, of Clause 60 of the 1923 CPC. According to that provision, the summoning of *ahl-i-khibra* was mandatory in cases to determine the cause of death and the nature of bodily injuries, as well as when doubts arose in the court or investigator regarding the mental state of the defendant or witness, in order to assess their mental condition [1].

In the 1961 CPC, issues related to the procedural-legal status of subjects with special knowledge – such as specialists and experts – were addressed alongside matters such as mandatory appointments for expert examinations and expert opinions, within the "Evidence in Criminal Cases" section of the Code. According to the second part of Clause 64 of this Code, the expert's opinion was considered one of the types of evidence.

The reviewed CPC's Clause 73 was titled "Mandatory Appointment of Expert Examination." According to the requirements of this clause, expert examination was considered mandatory in the following cases:

1. to determine the cause of death;
2. to determine the severity and nature of bodily injuries;
3. when there is doubt about the mental state of the accused or suspected person at the time the case is initiated, or whether they can understand their actions or control them, and if necessary, also to determine whether the accused or suspected person is an alcoholic or drug addict;
4. when there is doubt about a witness's or victim's ability to correctly perceive and provide accurate testimony regarding significant facts for the case, to determine their mental or physical condition;
5. when there are no necessary documents confirming the age of the accused, suspected person, or victim, and it is not possible to obtain these documents, expert examination is mandatory to determine their age if it is relevant to the case;

6. when an inspection was carried out without the participation of the accused and the results of that inspection are grounds for initiating a criminal case, expert examination is mandatory to verify the inspection documents that the accused does not agree with.

While commenting on Clause 73 of the 1961 CPC, the prominent specialist in Soviet criminal procedural law, Professor Jafar Hadji Hasan Movsumov, noted that the provision in Clause 73 of the CPC regarding the mandatory appointment of expert examinations is not contrary to the general rules of verification and evaluation of evidence. Specifically, it does not predefine the value of the expert's opinion and does not eliminate the necessity to use other evidence for the verification and evaluation of the opinion. In all cases, including the mandatory cases for appointing an expert examination, the expert's opinion is evaluated based on the law and socialist legal thought, with the court, prosecutor, investigator, and the person conducting the investigation examining the case in a comprehensive, complete, and objective manner, guided by their internal conviction [5, p.110-111].

Clauses 74-77 of the reviewed CPC were devoted to the expert's understanding, their rights and duties, the expert's opinion, and objections to the expert. According to the provisions of these clauses, a person with the necessary knowledge of specific issues arising during the criminal case proceedings could be an expert. The expert provided their opinion in their own name and was personally responsible for the objectivity of that opinion. The expert had the right to familiarize themselves with all the materials of the criminal case related

to the subject of the expert examination, to request additional materials necessary for providing their opinion from the investigating authority, investigator, or court, and to make requests before the investigation, questioning, and other investigative actions, as well as to participate in those actions with the permission of the investigator, prosecutor, or court. The expert could also ask the accused and witnesses questions related to the subject of the expert examination. If the expert considered the materials provided insufficient to offer an opinion, they were required to draw up an act and inform the investigating authority, the investigator, or the court in writing about the impossibility of answering the posed questions. According to Clause 76 of the 1961 CPC, titled "Expert Opinion," the expert would provide an opinion when scientific, technical, or other special knowledge was required to examine material evidence, documents, and other important aspects of the criminal case. The issues proposed to the expert and their opinion on these issues could not exceed the limits of the expert's special knowledge. The information determined by the expert's opinion, like any other evidence in the case, had to be verified and evaluated by the investigating authority, the investigator, prosecutor, and court in relation to all the facts of the case.

If the investigating authority, investigator, prosecutor, or court disagreed with the expert's opinion due to it being unclear or incomplete, they could appoint an additional expert examination by the same or a different expert. If they disagreed with the expert's opinion due to its baselessness, they could appoint a re-examination by another expert or group of experts. An expert could not participate in a criminal case if they were dependent on the victim or accused in terms of service or other relationships; if their examination materials served as the basis for initiating the criminal case; if they had participated as a specialist in medical expertise (except for a doctor's participation in the external examination of the deceased); if their authority was found to be insufficient; or in the cases listed in Clause 28 of the CPC (e.g., the expert was the victim, civil claimant, civil defendant, or a relative of the accused or any of these persons; the expert had participated as a witness, specialist, translator, judge, or lay judge; or if they had a direct interest in the outcome of the case). However, previous participation as an expert in the case was not considered a reason for objection [2].

It is interesting that when the 1961 CPC was adopted, its initial version did not include an independent provision regulating the participation of specialists in the criminal process. However, after a short period, the Supreme Soviet Presidium of the Azerbaijan SSR issued a decree on December 23, 1966, adding Clause 77-1 titled "Participation of a Specialist" to the CPC. The significance of this event for Azerbaijani criminal procedural law lies in the fact that with the addition of this clause to the legislation, for the first time, the procedural status of a subject possessing special knowledge (a specialist) was regulated more precisely than it had been in previous versions of the CPC.

According to the provisions of the new clause, in cases specified by law, the investigator could call a spe-

cialist to participate in an investigative action if the specialist had no interest in the outcome of the case. The request for the specialist's participation was binding on the head of the organization or institution where the specialist worked. Before beginning the investigative action in which the specialist would participate, the investigator was required to determine the specialist's identity and qualifications and clarify their relationship to the accused and the victim. After this, the investigator had to explain the specialist's rights and duties, warn them about their responsibility for refusing or evading their duties, and make a note of this in the relevant investigative action protocol. The specialist's signature on the protocol confirmed that these actions had been carried out. The specialist, when called, was obliged to attend the investigative action, assist the investigator in detecting, formalizing, and taking evidence using their specialized knowledge and skills, draw the investigator's attention to any issues related to the detection and documentation of evidence, and provide explanations regarding the actions they carried out.

At the same time, the provision of information to be recorded in the protocol regarding the detection, formalization, and collection of evidence was recognized as the specialist's right.

If the specialist refused or evaded fulfilling their duties, public measures could be applied to them, or the court could impose a fine.

From the perspective of the retrospective study of the use of special knowledge in criminal proceedings, Chapter 15 of the 1961 CPC also holds interest. Titled "Conducting Expert Examinations," this chapter contained independent provisions regarding the following matters:

- 1) Appointment of an expert examination during the preliminary investigation (Clause 181);
- 2) Participation of the investigator in the expert examination (Clause 182);
- 3) Collection of samples for comparative research (Clause 183);
- 4) Rights of the accused when an expert examination is appointed or conducted (Clause 184);
- 5) Explaining the rights and duties of the expert (Clause 185);
- 6) Expert opinion during the preliminary investigation (Clause 186);
- 7) Informing the accused of the expert opinion (Clause 187);
- 8) Hospitalization of the accused or suspected person in a medical institution (Clause 188).

If we were to give a brief overview of the listed items, we could mention that, according to the established rules, if the investigator deems it necessary to conduct an expert examination, a decision should be made regarding this. The decision must include the grounds for appointing the expert examination, the expert's surname, and the name of the institution where the examination will be conducted. The matters the expert should address must be explained, and the materials given to the expert for review must be specified. If the investigator considers the expert's opinion to be in-

complete or unclear, a decision should be made for additional expert examination by the same or another expert. If the investigator considers the expert's opinion to be unsupported, a decision should be made for a repeat examination by another expert. The investigator had the right to participate in the examination. The investigator could be present during the forensic medical examination of a deceased person. In the 1961 Criminal Procedure Code (CPC), the act of collecting samples for comparative research was also regulated under the "Conducting Expert Examination" section. Clause 183 of the CPC allowed the investigator to take samples of the perpetrator's or suspect's handwriting, traces, or other necessary samples for comparative research. The investigator was required to issue a decision regarding the collection of samples and a protocol for the process. A positive aspect of the 1961 CPC was the existence of an independent clause regarding the rights of the accused during the appointment and conduct of expert examinations. According to this clause, the accused had the following rights when an examination was being appointed and conducted:

- To object to the expert;
- To request the appointment of an expert from the persons indicated by them;
- To suggest additional questions to the expert;
- To participate in the examination with the investigator's permission and provide explanations to the expert;
- To submit additional documents;
- To familiarize themselves with the results of the examination.

Similarly, the existence of an independent clause regarding the expert's opinion in the 1961 CPC should be considered a positive feature. According to this clause, the expert was required to conduct necessary research and prepare an opinion. The opinion must include information about when and where the examination took place, the expert's surname, name, patronymic, education, specialization, academic degree or title, and position held, as well as who conducted the examination, its subject, the methods used, the materials the expert worked with, and who participated in the examination. After that, the expert should explain the grounds for their conclusion and address the questions posed to them. If the expert identified relevant facts that were not explicitly stated in the assignment, they were

entitled to include these in their opinion. After reviewing the expert's opinion, the investigator could summon the expert for clarification or to add additional information.

An independent Clause 310 in the 1961 CPC addressed the issue of conducting an expert examination in court. According to this clause, an expert called by the court participated in the investigation of evidence and, with the court's permission, could ask the defendant, the victim, and witnesses questions about important matters relevant to the expert's opinion. After clarifying all relevant issues, the presiding judge would suggest that the prosecutor, public prosecutor, defendant, defense attorney, public defender, victim, civil claimant, civil defendant, and their representatives submit written questions to the expert. The court would review these questions, remove those unrelated to the case or the expert's role, and, on its own initiative, formulate questions for the expert. The presiding judge would announce the questions for the expert, hear the opinions of the participants in the trial, and the prosecutor's view, and then the expert would begin to draft their opinion. The expert would submit their opinion in writing and announce it in the court session. The questions posed to the expert and the expert's opinion would be added to the case file. The expert was also entitled to include results for issues not explicitly raised by the court but which were relevant to the case in their opinion. The presiding judge, lay judges, and other listed individuals could also ask the expert questions to clarify their opinion. The oral questions posed to the expert and their responses had to be recorded in the court's session protocol.

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